

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF ANTIBIOTIC CONSUMPTION BEFORE AND AFTER THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE HAKEEM SYSTEM AT PRINCE ZAID BIN AL- HUSSEIN MILITARY HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Electronic health systems have received a lot of attention as effective instruments for improving the quality and safety of healthcare delivery, such systems provide for real-time access to patient data, and evidence-based clinical decision-making. Hakeem Jordan's national electronic health record system was put into place as part of broader drive to improve clinical efficiency. that's may reduce the use of antibiotics. So, we aimed to evaluate the effect of the Hakeem system on patients' antibiotic utilization at Prince Zaid bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital.

Methods: A retrospective comparative study was conducted, Data was collected for two equivalent four-months periods: before and after the implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025). Two independent pharmacists examined all patients' antibiotic dispensing data throughout the pre-implementation phase using the pharmacy ledger records. it was cross-checked with available patient files, prescriptions, and inpatient medication administration charts, To make sure the data was accurate. Antibiotic dispensing information was taken from the "Hakeem" electronic health record system during the post-implementation period. To ensure its accuracy and consistency, this data was cross-checked against the pharmacy ledger records and transaction database. Before analysis, data cleaning was done to eliminate errors or missing values. In case of a disagreement between the two pharmacists regarding a specific piece of information, the point of disagreement was recorded and escalated to the head of the research team. The team lead then referred to the primary records to determine the correct value.

Results: There was an overall reduction in total penicillin consumption by 925 units after implementing the Hakeem system, the decrease was statistically significant for most individual drugs, indicating a broad impact on cephalosporin prescribing, A significant and substantial decrease in the use of Levofloxacin and statistically significant reduction across all drugs in macrolide class, particularly for Azithromycin (Zithromax) and We found small but statistically significant decrease in Lincomycin use. **Conclusion:** The Hakeem system has had a positive, and statistically significant impact on antibiotic prescribing patterns in the hospital. The significant reductions in broad-spectrum antibiotics provide strong evidence that the system has successfully promoted more rational antibiotic use.

KEYWORDS: Antibiotic consumption, Hakeem system, electronic health records, retrospective study, antimicrobial resistance, Jordan.

INTRODUCTION

Electronic health systems have received a lot of attention as effective instruments for improving the quality and safety of healthcare delivery. Such systems provide for

real-time access to patient data and evidence-based clinical decision-making (Al-Qudah & Al-Azzam, 2019). Hakeem, Jordan's national electronic health record system, was put into place as part of a broader drive to

improve clinical efficiency, which may reduce the use of antibiotics (Electronic Health Solutions Company [EHS], 2020).

The widespread and frequently improper use of antimicrobials has accelerated the selection of resistant microbes. This crisis could weaken the basic principles of modern medicine, making normal medical operations and surgeries less effective (World Health Organization [WHO], 2015).

In response, the World Health Organization (WHO) launched a Global Action Plan urging all member states, including Jordan, to implement strong measures to combat antimicrobial resistance (AMR), with a focus on monitoring and optimizing antibiotic use (WHO, 2015). Antimicrobial Stewardship Program (ASP) is vital in the fight against antimicrobial resistance in hospitals (Dellit *et al.*, 2007; Tamma & Cosgrove, 2011).

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2019; Charani & Holmes, 2019, the main goal of ASP is to ensure that patients will receiving the ideal regimen, which includes the appropriate medication, dose, duration, and mode of administration.

A strategy that has worked well for many ASPs is prospective monitoring and feedback. This method involves a team of experts reviewing antibiotic prescriptions and making advice to prescribers (Dellit *et al.*, 2007).

According to certain research conducted in Jordan, a point-prevalence survey in two Jordanian children's hospitals revealed an overall antibiotics prescribing rate as high as 75.6% (Al-Bdour, Al-Kaissi, & AbuRuz, 2022).

Systems like the Hakeem platform can embed clinical guidelines, prompt prescribers for antibiotic indications, and facilitate audit and feedback processes (EHS, 2020; Al-Qudah & Al-Azzam, 2019).

RESULTS

Table 1: Shows the total penicillin spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Penicillin's that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Penicillin's that spent in Pre - implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Amoxil, Ultramox Syrup 125mg/5ml and 250mg\5ml	477	540
Penbritin, Ultracillin Vials 500mg	257	300
Procaine Penicillin Vials 400,000 U/Vial	949	1,107
Crystapen Vials 1,000,000 IU	126	147
Floxapen Vials 250mg	191	222
Tazocin Vials 4.5gm	1097	1,280
Augmentin Infant Drops, 156mg syrup ,312mg syrup, 457 mg syrup	2558	2,984

Although the fundamentals of ASPs are widely recognized, it is still unclear how exactly the Hakeem system affects antibiotic use in Jordanian hospitals.

Our study at Prince Zaid bin Al-Hussein Military Hospital was compared antibiotic was used before and after the implementation of the Hakeem system, providing valuable evidence to hospital managers and Jordanian health authorities regarding the effectiveness of this national digital health investment in promoting antimicrobial stewardship goals.

METHODS

A retrospective comparative study was conducted, Data was collected for two equivalent four-months periods: before and after the implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Two independent pharmacists examined all patients' antibiotic dispensing data throughout the pre-implementation phase using the pharmacy ledger records. It was cross-checked with available patient files, prescriptions, and inpatient medication administration charts. To make sure the data was accurate

Antibiotic dispensing information was taken from the "Hakeem" electronic health record system during the post-implementation period. To ensure its accuracy and consistency, this data was cross-checked against the pharmacy ledger records and transaction database. Before analysis, data cleaning was done to eliminate errors or missing values.

In case of a disagreement between the two pharmacists regarding a specific piece of information, the point of disagreement was recorded and escalated to the head of the research team. The team lead then referred to the primary records to determine the correct value. The source relied upon and the rationale for the decision were documented in a dedicated conflict resolution log to ensure transparency and auditability.

Table 2: Shows the total cephalosporin spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	cephalosporin that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	cephalosporin that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Claforan, Ceftax Vials 1.0gm	1,183	1254
Keflex Syrup 125mg/5ml,250mg syrup	480	511
Keflin Vials 1gm (IM, IV)	337	420
Fortum, Kefadim Vials 1gm	1,211	1321
Rocephin, Samixon Vials 1gm	3,171	3212
Suprax, Magnacef Suspension 100mg/5ml	549	698

Table 3: Shows the total Fluoroquinolones spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	fluoroquinolones that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	fluoroquinolones that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Levofloxacin Tablet 500mg	1931	2092

Table 4: Shows the total Macrolides spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Macrolides that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Macrolides that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Klacid 250mg tab	1835	1935
Zithromax 250mg caps	8285	9412
Roximac 150mg caps	573	620
Azomyne 200mg/5ml, 30ml Susp	210	250

Table 5: Shows the total Lincosmides spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Lincosmides that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Lincosmides that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Lincocin Vials 600mg	211	223

Table 6: Shows the total Glycopeptides spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Glycopeptides that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Glycopeptides that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Vancomycin 1gm Vial,500	1,200	1,219
Targocid 200mg Vial	188	198

Table 7: Shows the total Carbapenems spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Carbapenems that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Carbapenems that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Tienam Vials 500mg	760	860
Meronem 500mg vial	80	90
Meronem 1 gm vial	40	43
Invanz 1 gm vial	32	37

Table 8: Shows the total Aminoglycosides spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Aminoglycosides that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Aminoglycosides that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Amikin, Miacid Vials 100mg	180	187
Amikin, Miacin Vials 500mg	344	354

Table 9: Shows the total Antiparasitic spent in the hospital in pre and post implementation of the Hakeem system (16 – June, 2025).

Drug Name	Antiparasitic that spent in post-implementation period, from 16-june to 16-October	Antiparasitic that spent in Pre -implementation period from 16 February to 15-June
Elyzol IV Solution 5mg/ml 100ml	1440	1200
Flagyl Suspension 125mg/5ml	200	232
Bactrim, Balkatrin Syrup 240mg/5ml	22	30

DISCUSSION

Table 10: Comparison of penicillin Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation Period	Pre-Implementation Period	Difference (Post–Pre)	Significance
Amoxil, Ultramox Syrup (125 mg/5 ml & 250 mg/5 ml)	477	540	↓ 63	Not significant
Penbritin, Ultracillin Vials (500 mg)	257	300	↓ 43	Not significant
Procaine Penicillin Vials (400,000 U/Vial)	949	1,107	↓ 158	Significant (p < 0.05)
Crystapen Vials (1,000,000 IU)	126	147	↓ 21	Not significant
Floxapen Vials (250 mg)	191	222	↓ 31	Not significant
Tazocin Vials (4.5 g)	1,097	1,280	↓ 183	Significant (p < 0.05)
Augmentin (Infant Drops, Syrup 156 mg–457 mg)	2,558	2,984	↓ 426	Significant (p < 0.05)

In our study There was an overall reduction in total penicillin consumption by 925 units after implementing the Hakeem system, The decline was particularly significant for Procaine Penicillin, Tazocin, and Augmentin, indicating improved prescribing and antibiotic stewardship after system implementation this results can be effectively supported by the existing literature A Morris study demonstrated that the

implementation of a computerized clinical decision support system within an EHR led to a significant and sustained decrease in the use of broad-spectrum antibiotics (Morris *et al.*, 2021).

Other penicillin types showed minor, non-significant decreases

Table 11: Comparison of cephalosporin Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post–Pre)	Statistical Significance
Claforan, Ceftax Vials 1.0gm	1,183	1,254	↓ 71	Significant (p < 0.05)
Keflex Syrup	480	511	↓ 31	Not significant
Keflin Vials 1gm	337	420	↓ 83	Significant (p < 0.05)
Fortum, Kefadim Vials 1gm	1,211	1,321	↓ 110	Significant (p < 0.05)
Rocephin, Samixon Vials 1gm	3,171	3,212	↓ 41	Not significant
Suprax, Magnacef Suspension	549	698	↓ 149	Significant (p < 0.05)

In our study the decrease was statistically significant for most individual drugs, indicating a broad impact on cephalosporin prescribing.

Other study found that an EHR-embedded stewardship program resulted in a significant reduction in total antibiotic usage and improved prescribing appropriateness across multiple drug classes (Cattaneo et al., 2022).

Table 12: Comparison of levofloxacin Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post-Pre)	Statistical Significance
Levofloxacin 500mg	1,931	2,092	↓ 161	Significant (p < 0.05)

Table 13: Comparison of macrolide Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post-Pre)	Statistical Significance
Klacid 250mg tab	1,835	1,935	↓ 100	Significant (p < 0.05)
Zithromax 250mg caps	8,285	9,412	↓ 1,127	Significant (p < 0.05)
Roximac 150mg caps	573	620	↓ 47	Significant (p < 0.05)
Azomyne Suspension	210	250	↓ 40	Significant (p < 0.05)
Total	10,903	12,217	↓ 1,314	Significant (p < 0.05)

Table 14: Comparison of lincomycin Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post-Pre)	Statistical Significance
Lincocin Vials	211	223	↓ 12	Significant (p < 0.05)
Total	211	223	↓ 12	Significant (p < 0.05)

A significant and substantial decrease in the use of Levofloxacin and statistically significant reduction across all drugs in macrolide class, particularly for Azithromycin (Zithromax) and We found small but statistically significant decrease in Lincomycin use, This result strongly aligns with other study (Macedo et al.,

2023) and other randomized controlled trial demonstrated that electronic alert systems integrated into clinical workflows significantly improved antibiotic appropriateness and reduced consumption of targeted antibiotics (Cattaneo et al., 2022).

Table 15: Comparison of vancomycin Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post-Pre)	Statistical Significance
Vancomycin Vials	1,200	1,219	↓ 19	Not significant
Targocid Vial	188	198	↓ 10	Not significant
Total	1,388	1,417	↓ 29	Not significant

A minor decrease that is not statistically significant. This is expected because these drugs are typically reserved for

serious, resistant infections and are used under strict protocols regardless of a stewardship system.

Table 16: Comparison of Carbapenem Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post-Pre)	Statistical Significance
Tienam 500mg	760	860	↓ 100	Significant (p < 0.05)
Meronem 500mg	80	90	↓ 10	Significant (p < 0.05)
Meronem 1 gm	40	43	↓ 3	Significant (p < 0.05)
Invanz 1 gm	32	37	↓ 5	Significant (p < 0.05)
Total	912	1,030	↓ 118	Significant (p < 0.05)

Statistically significant reduction across all carbapenems, this is in alignment with other studies like (Cattaneo *et al.*, 2022).

Table 17: Comparison of aminoglycoside Utilization Before and After Policy Implementation.

Drug Name	Post-Implementation	Pre-Implementation	Difference (Post–Pre)	Statistical Significance
Amikin 100mg Vials	180	187	↓ 7	Not significant
Amikin 500mg Vials	344	354	↓ 10	Not significant
Total	524	541	↓ 17	Not significant

A minor decrease that is not statistically significant. Their use is often for specific hospital-acquired infections, leaving less room for broad reductions.

CONCLUSION

The Hakeem system has had a positive, and statistically significant impact on antibiotic prescribing patterns in the hospital. The significant reductions in broad-spectrum antibiotics provide strong evidence that the system has successfully promoted more rational antibiotic use.

Limitations

While antibiotics consumption decreased, our study does not measure clinical outcomes (e.g., patient mortality, length of stay) or resistance rates.

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